

A Comprehensive Review of Detoxifying plants

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Abstract:

Toxic chemicals are eliminated from organisms by detoxifying agents. They can be employed to reduce the toxicity of mycotoxins, repair organ damage, or shield organs during chemotherapy.

The process of detoxifying is quite important. Indeed, maintaining general health is aided by efficiently neutralizing and getting rid of pollutants. The most effective medicinal plants' ancient and contemporary uses, their active metabolites as detoxifying agents, the processes and pathways involved in the detoxification process, and the detoxification process itself are all included in this review.

Keywords: Giloy, Milk Thistle, Blueberry, Green tea, Liquorice, Cardamom

INTRODUCTION

The body's natural process of neutralizing or getting rid of poisons is called detoxification. This is primarily carried out by organs like the liver and kidneys. Plants containing compounds that can be used to treat or prevent diseases and promote overall well-being. Many medicinal plants possess properties that can support the body's natural detoxification pathways. Traditional medicine systems like Ayurveda, Traditional Chinese medicines, and Indigenous healing practices have long utilized plants for cleansing and purification [1]. A number of diseases including obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, CNS disorders and others may develop or worsen as a result of improper clearance and subsequent accumulation of toxins overtime. Silymarin and silybin are the principle active constituents present in numerous detoxifying plants. Silymarin has demonstrated the ability to enhance glutathione levels in people and safeguard the membranes of liver cells by strengthening the body's innate defenses [2]. Here we are going to review some herbs that help in detoxification. The

plant includes Blueberries, Green tea, Cardamom, Liquorice, Giloy, and Milk thistle. This review includes chemical constituents, synonyms and action of these plants.

1. *Vaccinium myrtillus L.*

Figure 1: *Vaccinium myrtillus L.*

Synonyms:

English: bilberry, wimberry, whortleberry, and huckleberry.

Tamil: Avirunelli [3]

Biological source:

Vaccinium myrtillus L. (bilberry) is a shrub which belongs to the family Ericaceae and genus *Vaccinium* and its habitat is mountainous regions in Europe, Asia, and North America.

Family: Ericaceae [4]

Chemical constituents:

Vaccinium myrtillus L. contains certain chemical constituents which include:

- Blueberries in a fresh form consist of water (84%), carbohydrates (9.7%), proteins (0.6%) and fat (0.4%) and so on.
- The total content of polyphenols in blueberries ranges from 48 up to 304 mg/100 g of fresh fruit weight (up to 0.3%).

- Flavonoids, procyanidins (monomeric and oligomeric form), flavanols (i.e., kaempferol, quercetin, myricetin) phenolic acids (mainly hydroxycinnamic acids) and derivatives of stilbenes.
- The anthocyanin content has been found to range from 25 up to 495 mg/100 g of blueberries, and it depends on fruit size, ripening stage, as well as on climatic, pre-harvest environmental conditions and storage.
- The percentage of delphinidin is 27%–40%, malvidin 22%–33%, petunidin 19%–26%, cyanidin 6%–14% and peonidin 1%–5% [5].

Detoxifying Action:

Blueberries help to combat the effects of oxidative stress that cause chronic diseases like diabetes, heart disease, and some types of cancer [2]. Vitamin C is known to be highly affected by a variety of environmental factors including oxygen, pH, light, temperature and moisture content. If the skin was damaged, the ascorbic acid was released and could be oxidized, and the concentration in the fruit significantly reduced. The freeze-dried blueberry sample revealed a low amount of ascorbic acid when compared to the dried sample. This might be because of significant loss of vitamin C during postharvest handling, processing, and storage conditions [6].

2. *Camella sinensis*

Figure 2: *Camella sinensis*

Synonyms:

English: Leaf tea

Japanese: Matcha, Bancha, Oolong tea [7]

Biological source:

Green tea, from the plant *Camellia sinensis*, is consumed in different parts of the world such as China, Taiwan, Japan and so on. It belongs to the family Theaceae [7]. The most popular one of green tea consumed is Sencha, most often made in Japan.

Family: Theaceae [7,8]

Chemical constituents:

- Green tea has a protein content of about 15–20%, which include amino acids such as l-theanine, tyrosine, tryptophan, threonine, 5-N-ethylglutamine, glutamic acid, serine, glycine, valine, leucine, aspartic acid, lysine and arginine.
- The trace elements such as magnesium, chromium, manganese, calcium, copper, zinc, iron, selenium, sodium cobalt or nickel, and carbohydrates such as glucose, cellulose and sucrose [7].
- Vitamins B2, B3, and C, as well as sterols and lipids like linoleic and α -linolenic acid, are abundant in green tea.
- The antioxidant potential of catechins with a pyrogallol group is higher than that of catechins with a catechol group.
- Catechins such as epicatechin, Epigallocatechin, Epicatechin-3-gallate, Eppigallocatechin-3- gallate [8].

Detoxifying Action:

It is a common nutraceutical which contains antioxidants which detoxifies the body. Antioxidants are substances that shield cells from the harmful effects of reactive oxygen species, including peroxy radicals, hydroxyl radicals, superoxide, singlet oxygen, and peroxynitrite. An Imbalance between the antioxidants and the reactive oxygen results in oxidative stress, which leads to cellular damage. Catechins help to protect against diseases by contributing, along with antioxidant vitamins i.e vitamin C and E and enzymes which contributes to total antioxidant defense system.[8]

3. *Elettaria cardamomum*

Figure3: *Elettaria cardamomum*

Synonyms:

English; Green cardamom, true cardamom.

Malayalam: Elam [9]

Biological source:

The *Elettaria cardamomum* genera belonging to the Zingiberaceae family is native to South India to West Malaysia. It is mostly grown in Kerala's Indian Cardamom Hills, which are classified as Cardamom Hill Reserves. The name *Elettaria cardamomum* was originated from the Tamil word “Elettari” [9].

Family: Zingiberaceae [10].

Chemical constituents:

- Alkaloids, anthraquinones, cardiac glycosides, saponins, tannins and polyphenols are present
- The seed contains phytochemical compounds such as phenols, starch, tannins, terpinoids, flavonoids, proteins and sterols [11].
- 1, 8-cineole (28.94%), α terpinyl acetate (26.7%), α -terpineol (14.6%), sabinene (13.5%), nerol (5.0%) and α -pinene (2.4%) 37 α -terpinyl acetate, 1, 8-cineole and α terpineol 38 α -terpinyl acetate, 1, 8-cineole, sabinene, linalyl acetate, linalyl acetate, linalool.

- Limonene (2.9%), 4-terpineol (1.4%), α -pinene (1.1%), β pinene (0.8%), myrcene (0.8%), octanal (0.2%), δ 3-carene (0.4%), p-cymene (0.7%), (E)- nerolidol (0.7%), cis-sabinene hydrate (0.6%), geranylacetate (0.3%), cis-sabinene hydrate acetate (0.2%), β -caryophyllene (0.2%), β -selinene (0.2%), γ -cadinene (0.2%), translinalooloxide (0.1%) 40 α -tocopherol, γ -tocopherol, δ -tocopherol, oleic acid, palmitic acid, linoleic acid_[12].

Detoxifying Action:

Antioxidant activities are related to oxygenated monoterpenes and phenyl prostanoids _[13].

Phenols, starch, tannins, terpenoids, flavonoids, proteins, sterols, anthocyanins, and alkaloids are the major constituents responsible for the detoxification _[14].

4. *Glycyrrhiza glabra*

Figure 4: *Glycyrrhiza glabra* _[15]

Synonyms:

English: Liquorice, Licorice, Sweet wood, Glycyrrhiza

Hindi: Mulethi

Sanskrit: Yashtimadhu, Madhuka

Turkish: Meyan or beyan _[16]

Biological source:

Liquorize obtained from the plant of *Glycyrrhiza glabra*

Family: Fabaceae

This perennial shrub is native to Asia and Europe and is widely used in traditional herbal medicine. It is also present in southern Italy, China, Spain, France, Greece, Germany, India, Russia, US, etc. [17]

Chemical constituents:

The major constituent of liquorice is glycyrrhizin, a saponin which is more sweeter than sugar cane and a glycyrrhetic acid. It also contains flavonoids like liquiritin, isoliquirtin, liquiritigenin, and rhamnoliquirilin. Volatile components such as pentanol, hexanol, linalool oxide A and B, α -terpeneol, and geraniol are also present. Asparagine is also found in the root of liquorice. [18]

Detoxifying action:

Liquorice has been shown to have a variety of pharmacological properties, including hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer benefits. [19]

The active components, such as pentacyclic triterpene saponin (glycyrrhetic acid) and flavonoids (liquiritin, liquiritigenin, isoliquirtin, isoliquiritigenin, and licochalcone A), were able to increase the expression of efflux transporters, such as P-gp, BCRP, and MRP2, which results in decreased absorption of xenobiotics across the small intestinal membrane. [20]

One of the most important classes of phytotoxins found in a variety of plant species are pyrrolizidine alkaloids (PAs). When used into herbal formulae, *Glycyrrhiza glabra* can both lessen the toxicities of some herbs and balance out their unpleasant characteristics. Glycyrrhizin and glycyrrhetic acid, two active ingredients, counteract the harmful effects of PAs and repair any possible liver damage they may have produced. Since cytochrome P isoforms are in charge of the metabolic activation of PAs, glycyrrhetic acid has been shown to have the capacity to suppress their activity. [21]

5. *Tinospora cordifolia*

Figure 4: *Tinospora cordifolia* [22]

Synonyms:

India: Guduchi, Amrita

English: Tinospora, Indian Tinospora

Hindi: Giloya

Sanskrit: Amritha

Sinhala: Rasakinda [23]

Biological source:

Tinospora cordifolia is a large deciduous climbing shrub belonging to the Menispermaceae family. [23]

It is established throughout the India & also in parts of Sri Lanka, Bangladesh and China. [24]

Chemical constituents:

Alkaloids: Berberine, palmatine, jatrorrhizine, magnoflorine, choline and tembetarine.

Glycoside: Syringin, cardifolioside A, and tinocordiside

Diterpenoids: Furanolactone, tinosporon, and tinosporides

Steroids: β -sitosterol and ecdysterone

Aliphatic compound: Octacosanol and heptacosanol

Sesquiterpenoids: Tinocordifolin

Essential oil: Hydroquinone, 2-hexenal, palmitic acid and phytol

Polysaccharide: Glucose, arabinose, rhamnose, xylose, mannose and galactose [25, 26]

Detoxifying action:

Giloy has an immune-boosting effect. It is said to have antipyretic, anti-allergic, and anti-inflammatory qualities. Additionally, *Tinospora cordifolia* exhibits hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, antiosteoporotic, anti-obesity, anticarcinogenic, antimutagenic, hypolipidemic, and hypoglycaemic properties. Giloy's antioxidant properties aid in skin detoxification. Giloy is also used to treat urinary tract infections, liver, and renal issues. [27] It is also reported to have anti-stress, wound healing and anti-HIV activities. [28]

6. *Silybum marianum*

Figure 6: *Silybum marianum* [29]

Synonyms:

English: Blessed milk thistle, thistle, Lady's thistle, Holy thistle, St. Mary's thistle

Germany: Mariendistel, Gemeine mariendistel

French: Chardon argente, Chardon marie

Russian: Ostropestro

Swedish: Sempertin

Spanish: Cardo asnal, cardo blanco

Romanian: Armurariu

Netherland: Mariadistel

Dutch: Mariendistel, Vrouwendistel [30]

Biological source:

It is obtained from the herbaceous plant of *Silybum marianum* which belongs to the family Asteraceae. The plant is native to Bulgaria, Egypt, Asia, North America, Africa, and Europe. [31]

Chemical constituents:

Flavonolignans: Silymarin including silybins A and B, isosilybins A and B, silychristin A, isosilychristin, and silydianin

Flavanoids: Taxifoline, quercetine, dihydrokaempferol, kaempferol, apigenin, naringin, eriodyctiol, and chrysoeriol

Sugars: Arabinose, rhamnose, xylose, glucose

Sterols: Cholesterol, campesterol, stigmasterol, and sitosterol

Lipids: Linoleic acid, oleic acid, and palmitic acid

Others: Proteins, tocopherol[30, 32]

Detoxifying action:

By raising the amount of glutathione in the liver, silymarin has been demonstrated to treat and prevent a number of liver disorders. Glutathione aids in the detoxification of medicines, carcinogens, and xenobiotics since it is involved in the liver's phase I and phase II detoxification processes. Silymarin helps repair liver cells damaged by alcohol, different microorganisms, and other harmful substances, while silibinin promotes the liver's ability to regenerate. [33, 34]

It is also reported to have anti-cancer, hepatoprotective, renal protective, immunomodulatory, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective activities. [33]

CONCLUSION

The review highlights that many medicinal plants support the body's natural detoxification systems. These compounds not only help in eliminating toxins but also play a role in preventing diseases by reducing oxidative stress and supporting organ health. Traditional

medicine systems, including Ayurveda and Chinese medicine, have long recognized these detoxifying plants, and modern research continues to support their therapeutic potential. Incorporating detoxifying plants into the diet and daily routine provides a natural and effective way to maintain long-term wellbeing.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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